

CULTUROLOGY

AN EXAMINATION OF LANGUAGES IN EUROVISION: THEIR IMPACT ON THE CONTEST'S EVOLUTION AND CULTURAL REPRESENTATION

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ABSTRACT

The article "An Examination of Languages in Eurovision: Their Impact on the Contest's Evolution and Cultural Representation" explores the role of linguistic diversity in the Eurovision Song Contest (ESC). It highlights the evolution of language policies in the song contest and how language selection has become a key tool for cultural expression and identity representation. The paper studies the shift from national language performances to English dominance in the 2000s, reflecting the global music industry. However, recent years have seen a resurgence of performances in native languages. This trend challenges the idea that performing in English is the best strategy for success at Eurovision. This paper examines the 2012 Eurovision Song Contest in Baku, Azerbaijan, as an important example of how Eurovision showcases both global trends and cultural diversity. The paper also explores Azerbaijan's shift after 2022, leading to their 2024 entry, which, for the first time, included some lyrics in Azerbaijani. The article uses examples of recent entries to show how non-English songs can relate to audiences, offering insight into evolving European cultural dynamics. The research concludes that Eurovision continues to serve as a platform for celebrating linguistic and cultural diversity while balancing global and local influences.

Keywords: Eurovision Song Contest (ESC), linguistic diversity, national languages, cultural representation, language choice, sociolinguistics, identity and language, English dominance, native language performances, cultural heritage, transnational identity, Eurovision language policies, globalization and music, multilingualism in Eurovision, cultural diversity in music, language selection strategies, national identity in music.

Introduction

With diverse artists, Eurovision also brings us **diverse languages** from different cultures, that's why language selection is crucial. This section explores the types of policies Eurovision has in place regarding languages, how language regulations have changed over the years, and also looks at examples of songs performed in native languages. The choice of language for the songs of the participating countries is sometimes controversial and is often seen as one of the most important factors affecting the outcome. Therefore, language is one of the issues that should be emphasized. As is well known, the Eurovision Song Contest is the longest-running song contest in the world since it was first broadcast. While Eurovision's website says that the contest was created to test the limits of live television broadcasting technology, it is also known that the EBU launched the competition to bring European countries under the same roof and unite people. One of the most controversial issues in Eurovision is the language in which the lyrics are performed. Initially, participating countries were allowed to present their performances in a language of their choice.

Language choice practices represent not just sociolinguistic macro-questions but also identity-based deliberate actions. Language selection is an important aspect of identity development in the ESC, and recipients who do not speak the provided languages will likely interpret it as identity-relevant. This way, choosing a specific language raises symbolic concerns (such as national allegiance or transnational European allegiance) unrelated to the denotational substance of the words used in the lyrics. Aside from the identity-targeted lan-

guage of songs, worldwide comprehension can influence language choice and, as is often the case, commercial growth.

The evolution of Eurovision's language policies

While there were rules about the duration of the songs performed, there are now no rules about the language in which artists can sing. The first participating countries Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Switzerland sang on stage in French, German, Italian, and Dutch. In 1966, Eurovision published a rule preventing participants from presenting songs in languages that were not official in their home country. From 1966 it became compulsory to perform in one of the official languages of the participating countries. This meant that the only countries that could sing in English were Ireland and the United Kingdom. [Mihalıs Kuyucu, 2002]

In 1973, the rule was changed again and participants were allowed to perform in any language they chose. In 1974, six of the seventeen participating countries (Finland, the United Kingdom, Norway, Sweden, the Netherlands and Ireland) performed in English. The choice of song language in the contest was revisited in 1977, revisiting the 1966 regulations, which once again made it mandatory for artists to present their songs in one of the official languages of their country. This rule in 1977 applied to all participating countries except Germany and Belgium, which were only allowed to perform their songs in English, as these countries had already chosen their song for the contest and were therefore allowed to take part in Eurovision exclusively. 22 years later, the EBU decided to enable countries to participate in any language of their choice and these rules remain in force today.

In 1999, when this rule was introduced, thirteen of the twenty-three songs performed were performed wholly or partly in English. Conflicts have arisen occasionally with this rule when performers have not used one of the official languages of their country and have chosen English instead. France's performance in 2008 is a case in point. Although one of the 2 official languages of the contest is French, the song "Divine" performed by Sebastian Teller, the representative of France in 2008, which was performed entirely in English, caused reciprocity and objection among the people

in France because it was the first time since the beginning of the contest in 1956 that France chose to participate in the contest with a song other than French.

From the 2000s onwards, the participating countries generally preferred English-language songs and concluded that their preference was more advantageous. If international artists are trying to consider the popular music market, English is the better choice than other languages, those other languages might be more successful in the local market. As seen from the table below, the English language winners have dominated the winning song languages in the contest starting from the year in question.

TABLE:

Winning Countries and Language Preferences between 2000-2024

Year	Country of the winner	Language
2000	Denmark	English
2001	Estonia	English
2002	Latvia	English
2003	Turkey	English
2004	Ukraine	English
2005	Greece	English
2006	Finland	English
2007	Serbia	Serbian
2008	Russia	English
2009	Norway	English
2010	Germany	English
2011	Azerbaijan	English
2012	Sweden	English
2013	Denmark	English
2014	Austria	English
2015	Sweden	English
2016	Ukraine	English
2017	Portugal	Portuguese
2018	Israel	English
2019	Netherlands	English
2020	Not Held (Cancelled due to COVID-19 pandemic)	-
2021	Italy	Italian
2022	Ukraine	Ukrainian
2023	Sweden	English
2024	Switzerland	English

The linguistic diversity of Baku edition

In 2012, in the finals held in Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan, most of the contestant countries used mostly English songs in their performances. So did Sweden's representative Loreen, who won this particular contest, with the song "Euphoria". However, three of the top five songs were not performed in English, but in the countries' native languages. Out of the 42 songs presented in the contest, 24 were in English, 12 were in

the mother tongue of the countries, and five were compositions in a mixture of English and the mother tongue. Two of these songs were sung in national minority languages (Finland's entry in Swedish, Russia's entry in a mixture of Udmurt and English). One song was sung mostly in Spanish with very few English lyrics (Romania's "Zaleilah" by a group called Mandinga). [Meijer, Albert, 2013]

It was curious that Romania sang its performance in a language other than its official language and English. A quick look at the 2002 Romanian ethnic census shows that the African Romanians are a small population in the country. They are not even listed and appear to be part of the category "Other ethnicity", which accounts for 0.07% of the population. It is noteworthy that Romania chose to represent itself with such a small minority, but it is not an uncommon strategy for Eurovision representatives to emphasize a multicultural, diverse ethnic image. It is interesting to note that occasionally in the context of the Eurovision Song Contest, a form of music that is not popular in the US is suitable for performance. Identification with Latin America is a common strategy for most Mediterranean artists. The "Hot South" performances use bright colors, rhythmic music and dance styles, and light and olive skin tones. These images constitute an exotic strategy in their own right. [Catherine Baker, 2008]

In the 2012 Eurovision Song Contest, Russia's entry, "Party for Everybody" by the Buranovskiye Babushki (Buranovo Grannies), was a standout performance, not just for its memorable ethnic staging but also for its unique linguistic blend. The song was performed in a combination of Udmurt and English, showcasing both a minority language and the global language of pop. The Buranovskiye Babushki were a group of elderly women from the village of Buranovo in the Udmurt Republic of Russia. Udmurt is a Finno-Ugric language, spoken by the Udmurt people, a minority group in Russia. By showing Udmurt in their Eurovision performance, the group brought attention to this lesser-known language, adding an important element of cultural and linguistic diversity to the contest.

Eurovision's language trends in recent years

The Eurovision Song Contest offers a snapshot of European multilingual practice. This list of participating countries will present language varieties and dialects. However, that attitude was developing conceptually with the start of the 21st century, and participating contestants were paying more attention to the role of their native language in communication processes. Singing the revived national language songs at Eurovision is indicative of bringing out the richness and independence factors of a country's roots. This sentiment was immortalized by Italy when it lifted the trophy in 2021 with an Italian-originated song "Zitti e buoni" by Måneskin, not only through the attributed talent of the musicians but also the distinctive cultural patrimony of Italy. "Zitti E Buoni," which translates to "shut up and behave," is a catchy, sensual song. Even though I can't understand a word they're singing, isn't that the point of Eurovision? I realized from the Eurovision Song Contest that you do not have to know the translation to appreciate the music. David's raw, fast-paced vocals are captivating, capturing his animalistic nature with a charming intensity. The band's youthful enthusiasm and great personality are on full display in the amazing music video. It's crucial to note that the Maneskin win, as well as the band's subsequent success, were not the result of pure luck. The band's management has been directed by an exceptional young manager named Marta Donà, who deserves a lot of credit for conducting

a highly planned campaign that brought the band to the notice of the larger Sony Music hierarchy.

Flash forward to 2024, the Eurovision Song Contest has slightly changed, especially in terms of numbers – more songs started to be performed in original languages. Nations are embracing their linguistic identity, what they have in their mouths is the beauty, the resonance that the world now gets to benefit from. This shift can be attributed to several factors:

Europe is gradually developing the necessary pride in oneself and one's nation and culture. Thus, countries are interested in promoting their singular language and cultural experiences, which they can do through Eurovision. Eurovision was always about inclusion and fully accepting other people as they are. Singing in native languages is something that fits into the contest's principles of diversity and equality. It is more effective to explore the language and cultural diversities of Europe and offers a more natural and diverse way of tuning into the music.

Fans and spectators of Eurovision have been realizing and acknowledging the use of native languages in songs. It can be seen that these performances are unique and have more of an impact, as opposed to many of the English submissions which seem rather similar. Of 26 participating countries in 2024, 15 preferred to perform a song in a language that is understandable for them, such as French, Italian, and Spanish. Other countries that opted for the use of their mother tongue include; Armenia, Estonia, Azerbaijan, Greece, Norway, Portugal, and Slovenia.

I keep up with nearly all of the contest's news as a member of one of Azerbaijan's largest Eurovision blogs. I have been very impressed in recent years by the shift in the Azerbaijani delegation on the song selection. Although the path changed, Azerbaijan has a history of sending English and Swedish-produced music. Azerbaijan has consistently worked with Swedish composers for many of their Eurovision entries. Of the 15 entries from 2009 to 2022, at least 9 songs have involved Swedish songwriters or producers. In recent years, they have tended to select local songs that have been written and composed by locals, which encourages people to produce their music and allows them to compete in the internal selection. Azerbaijan was among the countries that did not sing a song in their native language. In the last Eurovision edition, they broke the code and sent a song with lyrics in Azerbaijani. Although "Gəl özünlə apar" by FAHREE & İlkin Dövlətov, was not entirely in Azerbaijani, the chorus and title were in the local language. During the internal selection process, more local songs were sent in as the politics of the Azerbaijani song selection process changed. Now the broadcaster TV prefers local musicians to 'Swedish composers'. For the upcoming year, it is expected to be higher as the broadcaster İctimai TV shared the statistics on their official Instagram account:

'This year, 154 song applications were registered for the chance to participate in the Eurovision Song Contest 2025. It is pleasing that the rate of application of local musicians has increased from 43 to 49 interest rates.'

The resurgence of native language performances at Eurovision 2024 is a testament to the contest's evolving nature and the shifting cultural dynamics within Europe. This trend highlights a renewed appreciation for linguistic diversity and cultural heritage, making the contest richer and more varied. It increases our fascination with the Eurovision Song Contest as fans of diverse languages and cultures. Eurovision is all about Celebrating diversity. And language plays a major role in it.

Conclusions

In recent years, the Eurovision Song Contest has seen a notable move towards performances in native languages, challenging English's longstanding dominance as the language of choice for achieving success. Traditionally, English was considered strategic because many artists and broadcasters believed it made their songs more accessible and appealing to Eurovision's wide-ranging audience. Nowadays, however, an increasing number of countries are opting to perform in their own languages—a trend that highlights a growing appreciation for cultural identity, linguistic diversity, and authenticity on the Eurovision stage.

This shift towards performances in native languages has been marked by significant achievements. For example, recent years have seen songs not performed in English winning, like Ukraine's "Stefania" by Kalush Orchestra (sung in Ukrainian) and Italy's "Zitti e buoni" by Måneskin (sung in Italian), both earning victories respectively. These successes underscore the attraction of non-English entries and emphasize how linguistic diversity can engage audiences and judges when combined with captivating music, staging, and storytelling.

However, some countries, such as Azerbaijan, have not fully embraced this trend. Since its debut in 2008, Azerbaijan has consistently opted for English-language songs despite having a rich cultural and linguistic heritage. This approach likely aims to maximize broad appeal. Nonetheless, as the contest evolves to include more non-English entries, it prompts discussions about the potential advantages of incorporating native languages to assert national identity while still achieving competitive success.

Some authorities have always debated why English dominates the choice of language for songs. There are two reasons for this. First, English is understood and used as a language of communication by most Europeans. It is also true that there is a high percentage of easily understandable lyrics. Secondly, in the general pop music industry, artists singing in English are more easily appealing to an international audience. This language shows that the US dominates the modern cultural

landscape, as many song styles are derived from a distinctly American aesthetic. The predominance of English, often associated with a pop song, can be read as a desire to appeal to a broad taste of 'Western' or 'modernity'. However, not only in Eastern Europe but also in Western and Northern Europe, it can be observed that performances are mostly given in English.

Although English continues to be a popular choice at Eurovision, the increasing number of performances in native languages highlights the contest's expanding embrace of linguistic and cultural diversity. This evolution not only enhances the competition's cultural richness but also suggests that authenticity and cultural pride may hold equal or greater value than widespread accessibility for success on the Eurovision stage. For countries such as Azerbaijan, embracing a strategy focused on performing in their native language could potentially boost their engagement and representation within this diverse musical event.

For many years, Eurovision has served as an effective platform for representing various national identities, cultures, and languages. Beyond only music, the competition gives nations a chance to showcase their unique cultural and linguistic history to a worldwide audience. To celebrate their cultural heritage and add to the competition's rich diversity, an increasing number of performers have decided to perform in their native languages over the years. This acceptance of linguistic and cultural variety is among the most thrilling parts of Eurovision for viewers. It's fascinating to see how performers freely represent who they are, giving their songs a greater meaning and giving listeners an insight into their culture.

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